

Project information

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Introduction

The RIANA kick-off meeting was conducted on the 14th – 15th March 2024 at DESY in Hamburg. The workshop had 103 participants from Germany, France, Czech Republic, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Belgium, Switzerland, Austria, Greece, Lithuania, Estonia, Denmark, Spain, Romania, Netherland, Croatia and Norway. The majority of the participants (60 people) took part in person, while 43 people took part remotely via Zoom. Almost all project partners were represented at the kick-off meeting. The RIANA partners reviewed the implementation of the project and discussed plans for future work and meetings.

Photo: RIANA group photo of the kick-off meeting

Credit: Svenja Patjens

Description

The aim of the kick-off meeting was to present and explain the overall work plan and structure of the project as well as to clarify roles and align expectations – and, last but not least, to network and get to know each other in person after countless online meetings setting up the project.

In a welcome speech, the Chairman of the DESY Board of Directors, Prof. Dr. Dr. h.c. Helmut Dosch, highlighted the importance of the project for effective collaboration among Europe's research infrastructures and pointed out its role to advance nanoscience and nanotechnology.

The RIANA Project Officer of the European Commission held an Introductory statement and presented the basic framework of a Horizon Europe project. The first session was completed by a talk of Project Coordinator, Michael Stuckelberger (DESY) with information to the project consortium, the project structure, the project governance and the workflow of the user proposals. He also presented the project management team of the coordinator as well as the Executive Board members who were acknowledged on stage with a personal statement and cacti that were known from anecdotes during the proposal writing and GA phase.

After a group picture, the consortium split into several working groups dedicated to the individual project work packages. The aim of the WP-meetings was to discuss current action items such as WP kick-offs, work plans, tasks, roles, timelines etc. In the second part of the WP meetings, joint meetings were held between different WPs (e.g. WP6 and WP5, WP3 and WP4) practicing a direct exchange and alignment between the different WPs from the very beginning. The coordinator attended almost all meetings of the working group with different people in order to gain a comprehensive picture of the content of the meetings and to clarify open questions related, e.g., to the evaluation procedure of user proposals and the pro-active science and innovation support of users from academia and industry.

In the evening, a (net-)working dinner was organized to continue the discussions within and between the WPs and to develop further constructive ideas and solutions for the project. The coordinator gave a speech to strengthen the team spirit in the project.

But in order to get access to the dinner, the participants had to unlock a wooden door first that blocked the entrance. It was locked with 60 locks, one for each participant who had received an individual key beforehand. Only by working together, we can unlock the potential of 35 000 h access in RIANA.

On the second day, the work package (co-) leaders presented the 6 work packages including the outcome from the individual WP meetings to the entire consortium. Contents, goals, and connections to other work packages were presented and discussed. Tom Minniberger (DESY EU office) presented the requirements and rules in a Horizon Europe project with links to important reference information. In addition to the technical details of the presentations of WP2-WP5, the WP leader of WP6 presented a first draft of the internal and external communication strategy. Key outreach tools have already been set up and presented to all participants:

- The project logo is displayed in the header of this document.
- The website (www.riana-project.eu) is online in a first version and will be populated with more content as the project evolves.
- A linkedin channel has been established for timely broadcasting:
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/riana-research-infrastructure-access-in-nanoscience-nanotechnology/>

For broad advertisement of the webpage and linkedin channel of RIANA, QR codes have been shared with the consortium:

As side events of the kick-off meeting, the constitutive meeting of the RIANA Executive Board as well as the constitutive meeting of the RIANA General Assembly took place.

Photo: RIANA unlocks 35 000 hours access to Europe's leading facilities in Nanoscience and Nanotechnology
Credit: Svenja Patjens

Below, the following two documents are attached:

- (1) Programme of the RIANA Kick-off Meeting
- (2) Attendance list of the RIANA Kick-off Meeting. Note that few names and signatures of people who joined the meeting in person are missing.

RIANA Kick-off Meeting

When: March 14-15, 2024
Where: On-site at DESY, Hamburg (Germany), [building 5 - auditorium](#)
 Online via <https://desy.zoom.us/j/67035874683>
Who: RIANA consortium

Agenda

Wednesday, March 13, 2024

19:30	Informal Dinner (Restaurant "Herzblut St. Pauli", Reeperbahn 50, 20359 Hamburg, Directions; at own expense)
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Thursday, March 14, 2024

09:00 – 10:00	RIANA Executive Board (EB) Meeting building 1, 2nd floor, room 05 <i>Closed session (EB members, coordinator)</i>
10:00 – 12:00	DESY CAMPUS TOUR (registration required)
12:00 – 13:00	Registration and light lunch building 5 - auditorium
13:00 – 13:15	Welcome speech Helmut Dosch, Chairman of the DESY Board of Directors
13:15 – 13:30	Introductory statement Anna Santoro Policy Officer, European Research Executive Agency (REA), Unit C4 (tbc)
13:30 – 13:50	RIANA overview Michael Stuckelberger, Project Coordinator, DESY
13:50 – 14:00	GROUP PICTURE
14:00 – 15:30	Parallel session 1 (WP meetings); all rooms are in building 1, 2nd floor WP 2: Room 03a WP 3: Room 04a WP 4: Room 05 WP 5: Room 03 WP 6: Room 04b
15:30 – 16:00	COFFEE BREAK
16:00 – 18:00	Parallel session 2 (WP meetings)
18:30	Bus transfer to the restaurant (Meeting place: in front of DESY auditorium)
19:00 – 22:30	Working Dinner (Restaurant Parlament, Rathausmarkt 1, 20095 Hamburg)
22:30	Bus transfer to DESY (with stops at B&B Hotel Altona, NH Hotel Altona, Mercure Hotel am Volkspark)

Friday, March 15, 2024

09:00 – 10:00	RIANA General Assembly (GA) Meeting <u>building 5, auditorium</u> <i>Closed session (GA members, coordinator)</i>
10:00 – 11:15	WP presentations 1 <u>building 5 - auditorium</u> WP 1: Management <i>(20 min. presentation, 10 min. Q&A)</i> Michael Stuckelberger, Project Coordinator (DESY); Tom Minninger, project manager (DESY) WP 2: Customised access to scientific service <i>(10 min. presentation, 5 min. Q&A)</i> Regina Ciancio, WP Leader (AREA); Rafal Dunin-Borkowski, WP co-Leader (FZJ) WP 3: Customised access to research infrastructure <i>(20 min. presentation, 10 min. Q&A)</i> Doriana Orbanic, WP Leader (MAXIV); Daniela Stozno, WP co-Leader (Laserlab AISBL)
11:15 – 11:45	COFFEE BREAK
11:45 – 12:30	WP presentations 2 <i>(10 min. presentation, 5 min. Q&A)</i> WP 4: Customised access to innovation service Giancarlo Panaccione, WP Leader (CNR) WP 5: Training and education Panagiotis Loukakos, WP Leader (FORTH) WP 6: Outreach, dissemination, and impact Gaston Garcia, WP Leader (UAM)
12:30 – 13:00	Q&A, AOB, farewell
13:00 – 14:00	LUNCH
14:00 – 16:00	ARIE Network Chairs Meeting <i>(ARIE Network Chairs and Coordination Group; RIANA beneficiaries friendly invited)</i>